

A NEW SCALING PARAMETER FOR DELAMINATION GROWTH IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER FATIGUE LOADING

Matthew J. Donough^{1,2}, Andrew J. Gunnion^{2,3}, Adrian C. Orifici¹ and Chun H. Wang¹

¹Sir Lawrence Wackett Aerospace Research Centre, School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University
P.O. Box 71, Bundoora, Victoria 3083, Australia
Email: m.donough@student.rmit.edu.au, adrian.orifici@rmit.edu.au, chun.wang@rmit.edu.au

²Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures
1/320 Lorimer Street, Port Melbourne, Victoria 3207, Australia

³Advanced Composite Structures Australia
1/320 Lorimer Street, Port Melbourne, Victoria 3207, Australia
Email: a.gunnion@acs-aus.com

Keywords: Fatigue, Delamination, Fibre bridging, Finite element analysis

ABSTRACT

Mean loads or load ratios have a strong effect on the fatigue delamination growth rates in composite laminates. Semi-empirical models are used to predict this load ratio dependency behaviour. However the use of empirical models renders it difficult to predict fatigue lives subjected to variable amplitude fatigue loading and mixed-mode loading. This study presents a new scaling parameter that is consistent with the similitude principle and incorporates the crack-tip shielding effects of fibre bridging under fatigue loads. Static and fatigue, mode I and mode II experiments were carried out on IM7/977-3 unidirectional composite laminates. From the experimental findings, it was observed that large scale fibre bridging was a major toughening mechanism for mode I fracture under both static and fatigue loads. An inverse method was developed to quantify the traction stresses induced by the bridging fibres. The new scaling relationship, accounting for the fatigue bridging traction, is shown to eliminate the influence of load ratios on the mode I fatigue crack growth rates obtained in this paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite structures are inherently susceptible to delamination, which can subsequently propagate further under cyclic loads at load levels much lower than limit loads. In aerospace applications, a no-growth or slow fatigue crack growth design approach is taken to prevent cracks from reaching the safety limits. This is conventionally accomplished by employing low design allowable strains based on fatigue test validations. Although slow-growth (near threshold region) mode is permitted in demonstrating compliance with airworthiness regulations, the no-growth criterion is more commonly used, due to the lack of a better design criterion for slow fatigue crack growth of composites under fatigue loading. As a result, existing composite structure designs often carry additional weight to mitigate the risk of fatigue failure from service-induced damage. To fully take advantage of the lightweight characteristics of composite materials and to reduce the high cost burden of existing design practices, it is important to quantify the near-threshold growth behaviour to ensure the continuous airworthiness of composite structures during service [1] without excessive component and full-scale testing.

In contrast to metallic alloys, composite laminates are highly anisotropic and inhomogeneous. Consequently the strain energy release rate (G), rather than the stress intensity factor (K), is used as the correlating parameter as the solution for K is highly complex for inhomogeneous materials. Hence the fatigue delamination growth rates are typically described by G in a Paris-law relation given below,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta G)^m \quad (1)$$

where C and m are the fitting parameters and the cyclic strain energy release rate ΔG is defined as the difference between the applied maximum and minimum values [2-5],

$$\Delta G = G_{\max}^{app} - G_{\min}^{app} \quad (2)$$

It can be noted that ΔG does not conform to the similitude principle similar to ΔK (i.e. crack tip conditions are not uniquely characterised by a single loading parameter). A potential ambiguity can be highlighted for negative load ratios ($R = P_{\max}/P_{\min} < 0$). For example, ΔG equals zero under fully reversed loading ($R = -1$), because G_{\max} and G_{\min} are equal. Furthermore, this definition is unable to eliminate the load ratio effects in mode I and II fatigue delamination growth.

In order to avoid such ambiguity, an alternative definition of the cyclic strain energy release rate has been suggested which is consistent with the similitude principle as ΔK for a fully open fatigue crack [6].

$$\Delta G_{eq} = \left(\sqrt{G_{\max}^{app}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}^{app}} \right)^2 \quad (3)$$

However strong load ratio effects can still be observed in the mode I fatigue behaviour when correlated with ΔG_{eq} . As in the case for metallic alloys, this suggests non-linear conditions at the crack tip. The crack closure concept has been successfully used to describe this fatigue behaviour in metallic alloys [7, 8] and bonded joints [9]. However empirical fitting parameters are still need to correlate fatigue delamination data pertinent to different loads.

In addition to the need for extensive experimental tests to determine the necessary fitting parameters, the aforementioned empirical approaches are difficult to model the transient effect of overloads and underloads under variable amplitude loading, which is essential to the estimation of fatigue life under spectrum loading. Motivated by the great success of the crack closure concept in quantifying the effects of variable amplitude loading on the fatigue crack growth in metallic alloys, the present authors have recently shown that the load ratio effects on the disbond growth in bonded joints can be characterised by an effective strain energy release rate, once the plasticity-induced crack closure is accounted for. In contrast to metallic alloys and adhesives, fibre-reinforced composites are known to exhibit extrinsic toughening by fibre bridging [10-14]. The paper presents a methodology of quantifying the influence of fibre and, thereby, unifies the mode I and II fatigue delamination growth rates under different load ratios.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials and Specimen Preparation

Composite laminates were fabricated from 24-ply unidirectional IM7/977-3 pre-preg with a nominal ply thickness of 0.13 mm. A starter crack was introduced in the mid-plane by inserting a 13 μm thick Teflon film. The composite laminates were cured in an autoclave in accordance to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle. The test specimens were then machined from the laminates with a diamond saw into the following dimensions: 20 mm width, 170 mm length and a starter crack of $a_0 = 70$ mm. Additional piano hinges were glued to the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimens with a two-component epoxy. The side of the specimens were coated with a thin layer of white, brittle correction fluid to aid visual observation of the crack.

2.2 Static Test Procedure

Mode I and II fracture toughness tests were performed with DCB and 3-point bending End Notched Flexure (ENF) specimens respectively using an Instron 4466 with a 10 kN load cell. Schematic of the test configurations are shown in Figure 1. The initial crack position of the ENF specimen was placed at $a_0 = 0.5L$ to provide sufficient length for crack growth. Specimens were loaded in displacement control at a rate of 0.1 mm/min.

Figure 1: Schematic of DCB and ENF test configurations

The delamination length was measured visually from the travelling microscope. G_I and G_{II} were then calculated using the beam theory method and are expressed in Eq. (4) and (5) respectively.

$$G_I = \frac{3P\Delta_{applied}}{2Ba} \quad (4)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9a^2P\Delta_{applied}}{2B(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (5)$$

where a is the crack length, B is the specimen width, P is the reaction force, $\Delta_{applied}$ is the applied crosshead displacement and L is the span of the support rollers in the ENF test configuration. The initial fracture toughness G_{IC} and G_{IIC} was determined from the onset of non-linearity in the load-displacement curves.

2.3 Fatigue Test Procedure

Fatigue experiments were conducted on a computer-controlled all-electric Instron E3000 system with a 3 kN load cell. The specimens were subjected to constant amplitude, sinusoidal cyclic load with a frequency of 10 Hz under displacement control. A sharp crack was first introduced from the pre-crack under relatively high cyclic loads prior to the start of the experiment. The maximum applied load for the tests was chosen to be approximately 50% to 60% of G_C , determined from the static tests. After an initial 100 to 1000 cycles when crack growth was visible, the delamination growth rates were then recorded. The fatigue delamination growth rates in the Paris plot were generated using the load-shedding scheme prescribed in ASTM E647 [15]. Load ratios of $R = 0.1$, 0.3 and 0.5 were conducted for mode I tests and $R = 0$ and 0.45 for mode II tests. In order to account for the cyclic loads, the cyclic strain energy release rate is defined as ΔG_{eq} , given in Eq. (3). This definition was selected to characterise the delamination growth rates as it maintains the theoretical requirement of similitude under fatigue.

To characterise the effect of fibre bridging on the fatigue delamination growth rates, another set of tests were carried out using DCB specimens under a constant maximum strain energy release rates of 150 J/m^2 , $R = 0.1$ and 0.3 . To keep the maximum strain energy release rate approximately constant, the tests were interrupted after 0.5 mm crack growth. The applied displacement was recalculated and adjusted to maintain G_{max} corresponding to the new crack length. During the tests, the delamination lengths were recorded and used for determining the growth rates.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Static Fracture

Only one fracture toughness measurement per specimen could be obtained from the mode II tests as the delamination crack would grow unstably past the loading point in the ENF specimens. Conversely, stick-slip behaviour was observed for the DCB specimen. From an initial value of G_{IC0} , the fracture energy was observed to increase with delamination length. A steady-state fracture toughness, G_{IR} , was observed after an extension of 23 mm. The critical mode I and II fracture energy measured from the experiments is summarised in Table 1.

Specimen configuration	Initial Fracture Energy		Steady State Fracture Energy
	G_{IC0} (J/m ²)	G_{IIC0} (J/m ²)	G_{IR} (J/m ²)
DCB	100	-	240
ENF	-	1000	-

Table 1: Summary of static fracture toughness of IM7/977-3 composite

The J-integral approach was used to evaluate the static bridging law where the bridging fibres were modelled as a position-dependent traction stress that is a function of the crack opening displacement [16]. Hence, from the energy conservation, the fracture energy of an advancing crack is given as,

$$G_{IR} = G_{IC0} + G_{br} = G_{IC0} + \int_0^{\delta(a_0)} \sigma_{br}(\delta) d\delta \quad (6)$$

where $\delta(a_0)$ represents the crack opening displacement at the end of the bridging zone or the separation at the pre-crack location. G_{IC0} is the matrix material's intrinsic resistance to crack propagation, taken as the energy needed to propagate the crack from the pre-crack where fibre bridging is absent. G_{IR} is the total fracture energy required to propagate the crack, which can be inferred from the experimental R-curves. The crack opening displacement was optically measured at a_0 and the experimental measurements are shown in Figure 2(a). By differentiating Eq. (6), the static fibre bridging law can then be obtained, as shown in Figure 2(b).

Figure 2: a) Measured strain energy release rate versus crack opening displacement and (b) calculated bridging traction stress versus crack opening displacement under static loading

3.2 Fatigue Fracture

Figure 3 shows the relation between the delamination growth rates and the cyclic strain energy release rate ΔG_{eq} under mode I and II loading. Significant load ratio effects can be observed for mode I fatigue delamination behaviour, but not for mode II loading. The influence of load ratio under mode I, i.e. the higher the load ratio the faster the fatigue growth rates, is consistent with the fatigue behaviour of metals and bonded joints. This similarity indicates the presence of a certain mechanism affecting the crack tip conditions as in the case of metal and bonded joints where plasticity induced crack closure is identified as the driving mechanism. It is also observed that the slope of the mode I delamination growth rate is almost twice that of mode II. Similar to the static case, fibre bridging was also postulated as the cause for the observed mode I behaviour.

Figure 3: Relation between fatigue delamination growth rates and cyclic strain energy release rate ΔG_{eq} under (a) mode I and (b) mode II loading

A Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) image of the side crack profile of a fatigue specimen shows fibre bridging in the wake of the crack tip, seen in Figure 4. A second SEM image was taken at a second location. By increasing the intensity of the beam, the bridging fibres were observed to occur further within the crack. The bridging fibres induce a traction stress across the crack faces with the highest stress close to the crack tip and gradually decay. Given that plastic deformation of the matrix epoxy is likely to be negligible, fibre bridging is assumed to be the main driving mechanism for the observed load ratio effects in Figure 3(a).

In the constant ΔG_{max} test, the delamination growth rate gradually decreases with an increase of the total delamination length, seen in Figure 5. As the crack grows from its initial position, the fatigue bridging zone is very small. Hence the resistance to delamination crack growth, attributed to bridging, is small. As the fatigue bridging zone develops, the resistance increases, leading to a decrease in crack propagation rates. After a crack propagation length of 20 mm, the crack propagation rates were observed to attain a steady state value. Consequently, a fully developed fatigue bridging zone length was assumed to be 20 mm.

Figure 4: Schematic of fibre bridging in the delamination wake after it has propagated for a distance of Δa under cyclic loads

Figure 5: Fatigue delamination growth rates with increment of delamination length under constant applied G_{max}

While the methodology of evaluating the static bridging is relatively well established, reliable measurement of the fatigue bridging is yet to be proposed. Murri [10] and Zhang et al. [17, 18] attempted to normalise the fatigue delamination resistance based on the static results. This is established on the premise that the fatigue and static bridging are the same. However Stutz et al. [13] and Yao et al. [14] concluded otherwise. Hence analyses of the fatigue crack bridging was done and

compared with the static bridging law. The evaluation of the fatigue crack bridging cannot be easily done by the J-integral approach because 1) the precision of the optical measuring technique of small crack opening displacement without introducing significant errors and, 2) the applied sub-critical load amounts to a stationary crack under static conditions.

4 INVERSE SOLUTION OF FIBRE BRIDGING LAW

4.1 Method

The inverse method of deriving the fibre bridging law has two steps. Firstly, the crack opening displacements at different positions behind the crack tip were experimentally measured. This is denoted as $\delta = \delta(x)$, where x is the distance behind the crack tip, when the specimen is subjected to the maximum applied displacement Δ_{max} , shown in Figure 6(c). In the second step, the bridging parameters were determined from an inverse solution method. The traction stress induced by the bridging fibers is represented by a stress distribution acting in the direction perpendicular to the crack face, as shown in Figure 6(a) and (b).

Figure 6: Inverse solution method; (a) schematic of finite element model, (b) traction law due to fibre bridging, (c) crack opening measurements after steady-state crack propagation has occurred and (d) approximate number of design iterations per run

The fatigue bridging law is approximated as an exponential function and defined as follows,

$$\sigma_{br}(x) = \sigma_{br,max} e^{-\gamma\delta(x)} \quad (7)$$

where $\delta(x)$ is the experimentally measured opening displacement at distance x behind the crack tip, γ accounts for the rate of decay of the traction stress from the crack tip ($\gamma > 0$), and $\sigma_{br,max}$ denotes the maximum bridging traction stress at the tip of a steady-state fatigue crack. To find the appropriate values of γ and $\sigma_{br,max}$, a genetic algorithm available in commercial software ModeFrontier is employed to minimise the difference of the crack opening displacements between the experimental and Finite Element (FE) analyses. Mathematically, this corresponds to minimising the following cost function,

$$F(\gamma, \sigma_{br,max}) = \sum [\delta_{FEM}(x) - \delta_{EXP}(x)]^2 \quad (8)$$

where $\delta_{EXP}(x)$ and $\delta_{FEM}(x)$ are the crack opening displacements measured experimentally and computed by the FE model, respectively. The above cost function serves as the objective function to reduce the error between numerical and experimental values during the optimisation process. FE analyses were performed using commercial software Abaqus Standard v6.11. The substrate of the DCB was modelled using four-noded reduced integration plane strain (CPE4R) elements. The properties of the composite laminate are $E_{11} = 131$ GPa, $E_{22} = E_{33} = 13$ GPa, $G_{13} = G_{23} = 6.4$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = 0.35$. As shown in Figure 6(d), approximately 300 iterations were used per run to ensure convergence of the design parameters.

4.2 Results

From the inverse solution, the parameters of the bridging law were evaluated: $\sigma_{br} = 0.236$ MPa, $\gamma = 1.42$ under static loads and $\sigma_{br} = 0.225$ MPa, $\gamma = 3.2$ under fatigue loads. A comparison of the bridging law developed under static and fatigue loads is shown in Figure 7. In the case of the static bridging law, the inverse solution arrived at a solution that is approximately the same as the experimental method. Hence it validates the robustness of the inverse method. The steady-state fatigue bridging law is found to be different from one that is pertinent to critical loads, which has also been found by other researchers [13, 14]. The maximum bridging stress of the static and fatigue bridging law is found to be almost identical. However the fatigue bridging law has a much higher rate of decay in the traction stress than the static bridging law, suggesting further degradation of the bridging fibres induced by the cyclic loads.

Figure 7: Comparison of fibre bridging stresses under static and steady state fatigue loading

A cohesive zone model, schematically shown in Figure 8(a) was used to investigate the crack shielding effect on a stationary crack under subcritical loads as a result of fibre bridging. The cohesive element represents only the fibre bridging component (see Figure 8(b)) and is defined as: $k_{br} = 240 \text{ N/mm}^3$, $\sigma_{br} = 0.225 \text{ MPa}$, $\gamma = 3.2$ and $\delta_f = 1.5 \text{ mm}$. G^{tip} represents the actual strain energy release rate experienced at the crack tip and was determined using the virtual crack closure technique. G^{app} is the strain energy release rate calculated based on the global response of the DCB with beam theory.

Figure 8: Crack tip shielding analysis on a stationary crack using cohesive zone model; (a) schematic of finite element model, (b) fibre bridging traction law, (c) response of a single cohesive element during the loading-unloading process and (d) crack tip shielding mechanism as a result of fibre bridging

At an arbitrary crack length, the fatigue bridging zone must first be developed where damage is first introduced during the loading process. During the unloading phase, no damage occurred to the bridging law and it unloads in a linear manner (see Figure 8(c) and (d)). Hence, for any given load, the stress intensity factor at the crack tip is given as $K^{tip} = K^{app} - K_b$ [16]. Extending this concept to the strain energy release rate, the maximum and minimum G^{tip} is defined as,

$$\sqrt{G_{max}^{tip}} = \sqrt{G_{max}^{app}} - \sqrt{G_{bf}} \quad (9a)$$

$$\sqrt{G_{\min}^{tip}} = \sqrt{G_{\min}^{app}} - R\sqrt{G_{bf}} = R\left(\sqrt{G_{\max}^{tip}}\right) \quad (9b)$$

where $\sqrt{G_{bf}}$ represents the energy required to develop the fatigue bridging so that $\sqrt{G^{tip}}$ becomes non-zero. In this work, $\sqrt{G_{bf}}$ is defined as $5.53 \text{ (J/m}^2\text{)}^{1/2}$. Without fibre bridging, it can be seen that G^{tip} is equal to G^{app} .

5 A NEW SCALING PARAMETER

Having quantified the parameters of the fatigue bridging law and the effects of bridging on the crack tip, a new scaling parameter can now be defined to describe the delamination tip conditions for fatigue. By isolating the influence of fibre bridging, the crack tip conditions represent the intrinsic toughness of the matrix to fatigue crack growth. Hence G^{tip} is used to correlate with the fatigue crack growth. Therefore the effective cyclic strain energy release rate is defined as follows,

$$\Delta G_{eff} = \Delta G^{tip} = \left(\sqrt{G_{\max}^{tip}} - \sqrt{G_{\min}^{tip}}\right)^2 = \left(\sqrt{G_{\max}^{app}} - \sqrt{G_{bf}}\right)^2 (1-R)^2 \quad (10)$$

It can be seen in Figure 3 that the slopes of the mode I Paris curves are at least two times higher than the mode II Paris curves. This is possibly due to the material's sensitivity to G_{\max}^{app} under mode I loading due to the brittle nature of the matrix system, as in the case for adhesives [9]. The Forman model can then be used to account for the influence of G_{\max}^{app} [19]. Hence the Forman model is modified to account for fibre bridging and expressed as,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \frac{C_F (\Delta G_{eff})^{m_F}}{(1-R)\left(\sqrt{G_C^f} - \sqrt{G_{\max}^{tip}}\right)} = \frac{C_F (\Delta G_{eff})^{m_F}}{(1-R)\left(\sqrt{G_{IR}} - \sqrt{G_{\max}^{app}}\right)} \quad (11)$$

where $\sqrt{G_C^f} = \sqrt{G_{IR}} - \sqrt{G_{bf}}$ and $\sqrt{G_{\max}^{tip}} = \sqrt{G_{\max}^{app}} - \sqrt{G_{bf}}$ have been used. G_{IR} is the steady-state fracture toughness defined in the static tests.

Figure 9: Mode I experimental data under varying load ratios correlated with ΔG_{eff} by accounting for fibre bridging; (a) Forman plot and (b) Paris plot

At each experimental data point, the Forman model represents the data by computing the factored rate of delamination growth.

$$Q_{br} = (1-R) \left(\sqrt{G_{IR}} - \sqrt{G_{max}^{app}} \right) \frac{da}{dN} = C_F (\Delta G_{eff})^{m_F} \quad (12)$$

The correlations between experimental data of different load ratios with the Forman model are shown in Figure 9(a). A unique solution for C_F and m_F can be obtained which is derived to be 2.5×10^{-15} and 5.32 respectively, thereby eliminating the effects of load ratio. It can also be observed that the slope of the Forman plot ($m_F = 5.32$) is now significantly lower as compared to data before fibre bridging was taken into account ($m = 10$ for $R = 0.1$, $m = 12.8$ for $R = 0.3$ and $m = 15.7$ for $R = 0.5$). Although the slope is still considered high compared to conventional materials such as aluminium, the delamination crack growth rate may not be as sensitive to small changes to applied load as initially thought. This may enable designers to permit for very slow growth while still maintaining the benefits of a safe life design. In Figure 9(b), it can be seen that the crack growth rates in the Paris plot can be predicted by using the derived Forman parameters.

6 CONCLUSION

Significant load ratio effects were observed experimentally in the fatigue delamination growth of composite laminates. No existing correlating parameter is capable of mechanistically quantifying these effects. Hence traditional approaches have relied predominantly on empirical curve fitting. In this study, fibre bridging was identified as the prevailing cause for the load ratio effects in mode I fatigue delamination growth rates. The fatigue bridging law was derived using an inverse solution method. Therefore the effect of crack tip shielding due to the bridging fibres can be systematically studied and measured with the aid of finite element analysis. Consequently, a new scaling parameter was proposed to account for the crack tip shielding mechanism. In conjunction with the Forman relation to account for the strong influence of G_{max} , the fatigue delamination growth rates are now independent of load ratios. Hence the proposed scaling parameter is able to unify both mode I and II fatigue delamination behaviour.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was undertaken within the Robust Composite Repair project, part of a CRC-ACS research program, established and supported under the Australian Government's Cooperative Research Centres Program.

REFERENCES

- [1] FAA, Composite Aircraft Structure: Advisory Circular (AC) 20-107B, Change 1, FAA, 2010.
- [2] Schön J., A model of fatigue delamination in composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **60**, 2000, pp. 553-8 (doi: [10.1016/S0266-3538\(99\)00156-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(99)00156-6)).
- [3] Erpolat S., Ashcroft I.A., Crocombe A.D., Abdel-Wahab M.M., Fatigue crack growth acceleration due to intermittent overstressing in adhesively bonded CFRP joints, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **35**, 2004, pp. 1175-83 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.03.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2004.03.002)).
- [4] Hojo M., Ochiai S., Gustafson C.-G., Tanaka K., Effect of matrix resin on delamination fatigue crack growth in CFRP laminates, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **49**, 1994, pp. 35-47 (doi: [10.1016/0013-7944\(94\)90109-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7944(94)90109-0)).

- [5] Hojo M., Tanaka K., Gustafson C.G., Hayashi R., Effect of stress ratio on near-threshold propagation of delamination fatigue cracks in unidirectional CFRP, *Composites Science and Technology*, **29**, 1987, pp. 273-92 (doi: [10.1016/0266-3538\(87\)90076-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(87)90076-5)).
- [6] Rans C., Alderliesten R., Benedictus R., Misinterpreting the results: How similitude can improve our understanding of fatigue delamination growth, *Composites Science and Technology*, **71**, 2011, pp. 230-8 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2010.11.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2010.11.010)).
- [7] Wang C.H., Rose L.R.F., Newman J.C., Closure of plane-strain cracks under large-scale yielding conditions, *Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, **25**, 2002, pp. 127-39 (doi: [10.1046/j.8756-758x.2002.00483.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.8756-758x.2002.00483.x)).
- [8] Rose L.R.F., Wang C.H., Self-similar analysis of plasticity-induced closure of small fatigue cracks, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **49**, 2001, pp. 401-29 (doi: [10.1016/S0022-5096\(00\)00024-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5096(00)00024-7)).
- [9] Donough M.J., Gunnion A.J., Orifici A.C., Wang C.H., Plasticity induced crack closure in adhesively bonded joints under fatigue loading, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **70**, 2015, pp. 440-50 (doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2014.07.003>).
- [10] Murri G.B., Effect of data reduction and fiber-bridging on Mode I delamination characterization of unidirectional composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **48**, 2014, pp. 2413-24 (doi: [10.1177/0021998313498791](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998313498791)).
- [11] Sørensen B.F., Jacobsen T.K., Large-scale bridging in composites: R-curves and bridging laws, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **29**, 1998, pp. 1443-51 (doi: [10.1016/S1359-835X\(98\)00025-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(98)00025-6)).
- [12] Sorensen L., Botsis J., Gmür T., Humbert L., Bridging tractions in mode I delamination: Measurements and simulations, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 2350-8 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2007.08.024](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2007.08.024)).
- [13] Stutz S., Cugnoni J., Botsis J., Studies of mode I delamination in monotonic and fatigue loading using FBG wavelength multiplexing and numerical analysis, *Composites Science and Technology*, **71**, 2011, pp. 443-9 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2010.12.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2010.12.016)).
- [14] Yao L., Alderliesten R., Zhao M., Benedictus R., Bridging effect on mode I fatigue delamination behavior in composite laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **63**, 2014, pp. 103-9 (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.04.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.04.007)).
- [15] ASTM E647, Standard test method for Measurement of Fatigue Crack Growth Rates, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2013.
- [16] Suo Z., Bao G., Fan B., Delamination R-curve phenomena due to damage, *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, **40**, 1992, pp. 1-16 (doi: [10.1016/0022-5096\(92\)90198-B](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-5096(92)90198-B)).
- [17] Peng L., Zhang J., Zhao L., Bao R., Yang H., Fei B., Mode I delamination growth of multidirectional composite laminates under fatigue loading, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **45**, 2011, pp. 1077-90 (doi: [10.1177/0021998310385029](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998310385029)).
- [18] Zhang J., Peng L., Zhao L., Fei B., Fatigue delamination growth rates and thresholds of composite laminates under mixed mode loading, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **40**, 2012, pp. 7-15 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2012.01.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfatigue.2012.01.008)).
- [19] Forman R.G., Kearney V.E., Engle R.M., Numerical Analysis of Crack Propagation in Cyclic-Loaded Structures, *Journal of Fluids Engineering*, **89**, 1967, pp. 459-63 (doi: [10.1115/1.3609637](https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3609637)).